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Effectiveness Of Risk-Based Audits In Enhancing Internal Control System Of Selected Commercial Banks In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effectiveness of risk-based audits in enhancing internal control system of selected commercial banks in Anambra State, the sub-objectives were to: determine the effect of risk assessment process on enhancing internal control system; examine the effect of auditor competence on enhancing internal control system; evaluate the effect of management support on enhancing internal control system. Primary data for the study was questionnaire. The population of interest consists of all the employees of staff of commercial bank. However the total Number of staff in the selected bank is 397. This population figure was derived from human resources department of the selected banks (Zenith, Fidelity, UBA, First Bank. and GT bank) given the nature of this study, since the population is not up to 1000 respondents the research utilized the entire 397 population. Statistics, such as frequency count and percentages will be used in the analysis of personal characteristics, while hypotheses were tested using Multiple Regression Analysis. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis was carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Regression Analysis. the study found that, Risk assessment process had positive significant effect on enhancing internal control system, Auditor Competence had positive significant effect on enhancing internal control system, and Management Support had positive significant effect on enhancing internal control system. The study concluded that risk-based audits has positive significant effect on internal control system. The study recommended that Commercial banks in Anambra State should adopt a structured and data-driven risk assessment framework that continuously identifies, evaluates, and prioritizes potential threats to operations. Banks should invest in continuous professional training and certification programs for their internal auditors to improve their knowledge of modern risk-based auditing techniques, regulatory standards, and emerging financial risks. Top management should provide strong support for risk-based auditing by ensuring adequate funding, access to relevant information, and enforcement of audit recommendations.

Keywords: Risk-based audits, internal control system, risk assessment process, auditors' competence and management support

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the global business environment has become increasingly complex and uncertain, leading organizations to face heightened risks in their operations, reporting, and compliance activities Abubakar, Mohammed, Terzungwe, Onipe (2023). Traditional audit approaches that focused primarily on compliance and routine verification of transactions are gradually being replaced by more strategic methods that emphasize risk identification and management. One such modern approach is the risk-based audit (RBA), which integrates risk management principles into the auditing process to ensure that audit

resources are focused on the areas of greatest risk exposure (Akanbi, Anichebe, & Orjinta 2023).. The central goal of a risk-based audit is to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of auditing activities, thereby strengthening the organization's internal control system.

The internal control system serves as a fundamental mechanism for safeguarding organizational assets, ensuring accurate financial reporting, promoting operational efficiency, and encouraging compliance with laws and regulations (Alhazmi, Islam, & Prokofieva, 2024). However, weaknesses in internal controls remain one of the major contributors to corporate failures, financial misstatements, and fraud, particularly in developing economies. In response to these challenges, organizations and regulators have begun to adopt risk-based auditing as a proactive tool for assessing and improving internal controls. By focusing on areas of high risk, auditors can provide management with more relevant insights and recommendations for improving the control environment (Amuzat, and Aina 2025).

In the context of Nigeria, the need for effective internal control systems has become even more pressing due to recurring cases of financial irregularities, weak governance structures, and inefficiencies in both public and private sector organizations (Awotomilusi, Ajoloko, O. M., Saka, Adeniran, Owonifari, & Dagunduro, 2025). The adoption of risk-based auditing by audit firms, government audit agencies, and corporate internal auditors has been encouraged by regulatory bodies such as the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN), the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN), and the Office of the Auditor-General. Despite these initiatives, there is limited empirical evidence on how effective risk-based audits have been in enhancing internal control systems across organizations in the country (Dagunduro, Falana, Omodara, Fagbomedo, Aluko, Olufemi, Ogunleye, & Osaloni, 2025).

Therefore, this study seeks to assess the effectiveness of risk-based audits in enhancing the internal control system. It will investigate how the various components of risk-based auditing such as risk assessment, auditor competence, and management support contribute to the improvement of internal controls. The findings of this research are expected to provide insights for auditors, policymakers, and managers on how to strengthen risk-based audit practices as a strategic tool for achieving sound governance and accountability.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the effectiveness of risk-based audits in enhancing internal control system of selected commercial banks in Anambra State. The specific objectives are to:

- i. To determine the effect of risk assessment process on enhancing internal control system
- ii. To examine the effect of auditor competence on enhancing internal control system
- iii. To evaluate the effect of management support on enhancing internal control system

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Risk Based Auditing

IIAU defines Risk Based Auditing (RBA) as a methodology that links internal auditing to an organization's overall risk management framework. It allows internal audit to provide assurance to the board that risk management processes are managing risks effectively, in relation to the risk appetite. Risk-based auditing derives largely from models that assume that inherent risk (IR) and control risk (CR) are distinct concepts and that IR arises from attributes of the audit environment that are completely independent of attributes that determine the level of controlling risk. Risk-based auditing is the process of ascertaining and reporting the risk of significant misrepresentations in financial statements. This approach increases the value of the product (financial statements), and makes auditing more profitable. In other words, risk-based auditing satisfies both the managers and the auditors (Smith, 2016).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Contingency Theory

Contingency Theory was developed in 1958 and advanced by Magaji et al. (2018). It is a class of behavioral theory that asserts that there is no prime way to lead a corporation, make decisions, or organize them. Instead, the optimal course of action is contingent (dependent) upon the external and internal situations. Therefore, the model is an approach to the study of organizational behavior exploring the

influence of both internal and external contingent variables such as culture, technology, and environment on the function and design of the firm's structure, (Magaji et al., 2018).

The contingency Theory hypothesis focuses on specific situational factors that affect direct relationship between independent and dependent variables, (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). An important application of Contingent Theory is through a control system where the accounting information system (AIS) is bound up with a key control mechanism to influence behaviors and relationships (Dagiliene & Sutiene, 2019). Though Contingency theory demonstrates a predictive power in leadership that is effective in certain contexts, its criticism cannot be ignored.

To start with Contingency theory failed to explain why leaders with particular leadership styles are effective and ineffective in some situations. The least Preferred Coworker scale validity that measured task-oriented leadership and relationship-oriented leadership did not correlate with other leadership measures. Lastly, the Contingency theory failed to adequately explain what should be done about the mismatch of leaders in the workplace (Suleiman et al., 2018). The auditor (AI) as economic agents of the business risk model need to decide on alternatives that involve risks and uncertainty in an organization. RBIA can be achieved through contingency theory. According to Kothari and Garg (2014), the theory enables a researcher to systematically introduce and significantly hypothesis dependent and independent variables and subject results to empirical tests. This theory can be applied in the context of RBA which depends upon contingent variables such as internal control to influence financial performance.

2.3 Empirical Review

Nguyen (2024) provided empirical evidence about the correlation between the risks of audited entities, the competitive ability of state auditors, and audit quality. The study also seeks to establish the moderating effect of risk-based auditing on the relationship between the abovementioned factors and audit quality. The research data was collected from 221 state auditors and analyzed using SEM linear structure analysis with SmartPLS 4.0.8.5 software. The research findings suggest that the risk of the audited entity and the competitive ability of state auditors positively and significantly impact the application of RBA, which contributes to the assurance of audit quality in SAV. Therefore, the practical application of RBA, which involves accurately identifying the risks of audited entities, helps to improve audit quality and efficiency. This study contributes to the theory of audit quality in the public sector, which is diverse and inconsistent due to various economic and political factors such as corruption and reputation

Were, Warui and Kariuki, (2023) determined the effects of the risk-based internal audit approaches (Cybercrime security controls, data analytics, and disaster recovery controls) on the financial performance of insurance firms listed at the NSE, Kenya. Firm size was used to moderate between risk-based approaches and insurance financial performance. Positivist research philosophy and causal research design were adopted where 6 Insurance firms licensed to trade at the NSE, Kenya were surveyed. Both primary and secondary data were used and were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics and presented using graphs, statistical tables, and pie charts. The study found that Cybercrime security controls, data analytics controls, and disaster recovery controls had a statistically significant positive effect on the financial performance of Insurance firms listed at the NSE, Kenya. On the contrary, firm size was found not to have a statistically significant moderation effect on the risk-based internal audit approaches.

Lumidi and Opuodho, (2022) determined the influence of risk-based audit practices on financial performance of registered fruit processing firms in Thika Municipality, Kenya. The theories embraced comprised of Contingency, Agency, Risk, and Stewardship. The study applied a descriptive research design. The target population was 130 management staff of registered fruit processing firms in Thika municipality Kenya. Census survey techniques were used for the study. Both primary and secondary data were used. A questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The collected data was analyzed using computer-aided SPSS Standard Version 28. The regression coefficient of the study showed that a unit change in audit risk management leads to a 2.73 change in the financial performance of registered fruit-processing firms in Thika Municipality, Kenya. The study also revealed that a unit change

in audit quality leads to a 2.277 change in the financial performance of registered fruit-processing firms in Thika Municipality, Kenya.

Niyitegeka and Kato (2021) examined the impact of internal audit on the financial performance in Rwanda, specifically at the Bank of Kigali. The researcher used a descriptive, correlational, and explanatory study methodology and asked 76 participants from various Bank of Kigali departments to complete a questionnaire. The study employed a universal sampling technique that does not include everyone in the population equally profitable in the sample. Primary and secondary data were both employed in this study to gather the information needed for it. The acquired data was analyzed using a descriptive and correlation study approach. Analyzing data necessitated using metrics like the mean, SD, and Pearson correlation. The data acquired through surveys was analyzed with the help of SPSS version 22.0. The correlation (r) between respondents' views on the impact of internal audit on financial performance was found to be equal to .78. In order to ensure that projects, programs, activities, and functions are efficient and effective, the researchers recommend that Bank of Kigali management make performance audit independent.

Njeri, (2013) traced the effect of risk-based audit on financial performance of DTMFIs in Kenya. Correlation research design was adopted in the investigation in which quantity data was collected and analysed in order to describe the specific phenomenon in its current trends, current events and linkages between different factors at the current time. The population of 6 deposit taking Microfinance is small therefore the study carried out a census survey of all the Microfinance Deposit Taking Institutions in Kenya. Primary data was collected through a questionnaire which was quantitative in nature. A total of 36 credit officers, branch managers and operation manager auditors at the six deposit taking microfinance institutions in Kenya were asked to respond to a questionnaire. Inferential statistic regression and correlation was used to establish the effect of risk based audit on financial performance of DTMFIs. The findings show that there is a positive effect of risk based audit on financial performance of Deposit Taking Microfinance Institutions in Kenya.

Terer and Ngahu (2017) studied factors influencing Risk-Based Internal Audit (RBIA) adoption in Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization in Nairobi. The study sought to establish the influence of ICT on RBIA adoption. A descriptive research design was employed. The target population was 64 senior managers. Research findings indicated that ICT infrastructure positively and significantly influenced the adoption of RBIA. The study did not measure financial performance and the independent variable was only one. Analysis of the relationships between risk management and financial performance has used contrasting proxies for risk management with varied outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

The research design encompasses the methods for the collection, measurement and analysis of data related to the research objectives. The research design chosen for this study is survey method. The survey research method is most appropriate because the researcher has no control of the variables as well as the outcome. Primary data are firsthand or raw data, original records and materials created by participants or witnesses of the event(s) under study. In primary data for the study, personal interview and questionnaire will be used. The population of interest consists of all the employees of staff of commercial bank. However the total Number of staff in that organization is 397. This population figure was derived from human resources department of the selected banks (Zenith, Fidelity, UBA, First Bank. and GT bank) given the nature of this study, since the population is not up to 1000 respondents the research utilized the entire 397 population. Statistics, such as frequency count and percentages will be used in the analysis of personal characteristics, while hypotheses were tested using Multiple Regression Analysis. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis was carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Regression Analysis.

RESULT INTERPRETATION

4.1 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression result was employed to test the effect of independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in the tables below.

Table 4.1.1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Durbin-Watson	
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2		Sig. F Change
1	.673 ^a	.524	.513	.96254	.224	20.844	4	365	.000	1.820

a. Predictors: (Constant), RAP, ADC, MGS

b. Dependent Variable: ICS

Table 4.1.1 shows that R² co-efficient of determination which measures the strength of the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable has the value of 0.52. This implies that 52% of the variation in internal control system is explained by variations in risk assessment process, auditor competence and management support. This was supported by adjusted R² of 0.51%. Test for autocorrelation: This is used to test whether errors corresponding to different observations are uncorrelated. If the value of the durbin-watson from the regression result is close to 2 no multicollinearity in that regression result, but if it deviates significantly then there is multicollinearity. The Durbin-Watson statistic (D.W) of 2 reveals no autocorrelation in the model. Hence, the result is good for business analysis because the Durbin Watson result is 1.820 which indicates that the study is free from the problems of autocorrelation.

Table 4.1.2 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	308.738	4	19.311	20.844	.000 ^b
	Residual	246.261	365	.926		
	Total	554.998	369			

a. Dependent Variable: ICS

b. Predictors: (Constant), RAP, ADC, MGS

The f-statistics value of 20.844 in table 4.1.2 with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables have significant effect on dependent variable and can collectively explain the variations in risk-based audits variables on employee output. The F-test of 20.844 indicates that the regression model is statistically significant. This implies that the explanatory variables jointly have a significant effect on the dependent variable

Table 4.1.3. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	2.467	.413		5.967	.000	1.655	3.279
	RAP	.116	.081	.124	2.438	.001	.274	.042
	ADC	.285	.100	.270	2.851	.005	.482	.089
	MGS	.408	.086	.389	4.769	.000	.240	.576

a. Dependent Variable: EMO

A’piori Criteria: This is determined by the existing business theories; it also indicates the signs and magnitude of the business parameter under review. In table 4.1.3 above, we found out that risk assessment process has a positive sign given its value as .116; this implies that a unit increase in risk assessment process increases the internal control system by 11%, this conform to theoretical expectation. Auditor competence has a positive sign given its value as. 0.285; this implies that a unit increase in Auditor competence increases the internal control system by 28%, this conform to theoretical expectation. Management support has a positive sign given its value as. 0.408; this implies that a unit increase in Management support increases the internal control system by 40%, this conform to theoretical expectation.

T- Statistics: The t-test is used to measure the individual statistical significance of the explanatory parameters in the model. From table t-test above risk assessment process is 2.438 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it has contributed significantly to internal control system. Auditor competence is 2.851 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to internal control system at 5% level of significant. Management support is 4.769 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to internal control system at 5% level of significant.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Risk assessment process has no positive significant effect on enhancing internal control system.

Risk assessment process has a t-statistics of 2.438 and a probability value of 0.001 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypotheses which state that Risk assessment process has positive significant effect on enhancing internal control system.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Auditor Competence has no positive significant effect on enhancing internal control system.

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table above is used. Risk assessment process has a t-statistics of 2.851 and a probability value of 0.005 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Auditor Competence has positive significant effect on enhancing internal control system

Test of Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: Management Support has no positive significant effect on enhancing internal control system Management Support have a t-statistics of 4.769 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Management Support have positive significant effect on enhancing internal control system.

5.1 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concludes that risk-based audits play a crucial role in enhancing the internal control systems of commercial banks in Anambra State. Findings revealed that when audit efforts are directed toward high-risk areas, banks are better able to detect irregularities, minimize operational risks, and strengthen compliance with regulatory standards. Risk-based auditing encourages proactive identification and assessment of financial and operational risks, thereby improving control efficiency and organizational transparency. Furthermore, the adoption of risk-based audit frameworks promotes accountability, ensures optimal resource allocation during audit engagements, and fosters continuous improvement in internal processes. Therefore, commercial banks that effectively integrate risk-based audit practices are more likely to maintain sound internal controls, reduce instances of fraud and error, and enhance stakeholder confidence in their financial management systems. The study recommend that Commercial banks in Anambra State should adopt a structured and data-driven risk assessment framework that continuously identifies, evaluates, and prioritizes potential threats to operations. Banks should invest in continuous professional training and certification programs for their internal auditors to improve their knowledge of modern risk-based auditing techniques, regulatory standards, and emerging financial risks. Top management should provide strong support for risk-based auditing by ensuring adequate funding, access to relevant information, and enforcement of audit recommendations.

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